

ON THE t -CORE OF AN s -CORE PARTITION

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Abstract

Given two relatively prime positive integers s and t , J. Olsson proved that the t -core of an s -core partition ρ is again an s -core. In this note we extend this result to the case where s and t are arbitrary distinct positive integers.

1. Main Result

Let \mathbb{N} be the set of nonnegative integers and let $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Consider sequences $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_t)$ of integers from \mathbb{N} with $\alpha_1 \leq \alpha_2 \leq \dots \leq \alpha_t$ and $\sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_i = n$. Two such sequences $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_t)$ and $(\alpha'_1, \dots, \alpha'_t)$ are said to be equivalent if their nonzero terms are the same. A partition λ of n will then be defined as an equivalence class of such sequences.

A sequence $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_t)$ representing λ determines a corresponding β -set, namely $\beta(\lambda) = \{x_1, \dots, x_t\}$, where $x_i = \alpha_i + (i - 1)$. The equivalence relation on sequences induces an equivalence relation on β -sets. Two β -sets $\beta(\lambda) = \{x_1, \dots, x_t\}$ and $\beta(\lambda)' = \{x'_1, \dots, x'_t\}$ are equivalent if $t' - t = d \geq 0$ and $\{x'_1, \dots, x'_t\} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, d - 1\} \cup \{x_1 + d, \dots, x_t + d\}$.

We may write this as $\beta(\lambda)' = \{0, \dots, d - 1\} \cup \{\beta(\lambda) + d\}$. Then $f_d : (y, x] \longrightarrow (y + d, x + d]$ is a bijection between $\beta(\lambda)$ and $\beta(\lambda)'$. A hook h of λ is a pair of nonnegative integers $h = (y, x)$ where $x \in \beta(\rho)$, $y \notin \beta(\rho)$ and $y < x$. We say h has length s (t) if $x - y = s$ ($x - y = t$). A hook h of length s (t) is also called an s -hook (t -hook). A partition ρ is an s -core (t -core) if it contains no s -hooks (t -hooks). In particular, f_d preserves hook lengths.

Theorem 1.1 Suppose s and t are distinct positive integers and ρ is an s -core. Then the t -core of ρ is also an s -core.

To prove Theorem 1.1, we must define the s -abacus $\mathcal{A}^s(\beta(\rho))$ of ρ . We do so as follows: create s runners numbered $0, 1, \dots, s - 1$ running from north to south. In the i -th runner we place all non-negative integers of residue i modulo s in increasing order, and then underline

the numbers that occur in $\beta(\rho)$. These underlined numbers will be referred to as *beads* while the numbers that are not underlined will be referred to as *spaces*.

Suppose $\rho = (5, 5, 4, 3)$, $\beta(\rho) = \{3, 5, 7, 8\}$. Then $\mathcal{A}^3(\beta(\rho))$ is defined to be:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} 0 & 1 & 2 \\ \underline{3} & 4 & \underline{5} \\ 6 & \underline{7} & \underline{8}. \end{array}$$

The subset of beads on the i -th runner will be denoted $\beta(\rho)_i$. Removing an s -hook from ρ is equivalent to replacing an \underline{x} (in some $\beta(\rho)_i$) with $\underline{x - s}$. Notice $x - s$ is the position directly above x on the i -th runner. This will be described as moving a bead *one position north*. Then $\mathcal{A}^s(\beta(\rho))$ is the s -abacus of a s -core if for every $\beta(\rho)_i$ there are no available moves one position north (Theorem 2.7.16, [2]). The replacement $\underline{x} = i + ms$ on the i -th runner of the s -abacus with $\underline{x}' = i' + m's$ where $x' < x$, $i' \neq i$ will be described as moving a bead $x - x'$ positions *west*. (The reader is referred to Section 2.7, [2] and Sections I.1–I.3, [6] for further details on partitions, β -sets, hooks, and the s -abacus.)

Proof. When $(s, t) = 1$ the result is true by [5]. Suppose $(s, t) \neq 1$. Either (1) s divides t or (2) $\gcd(s, t) \notin \{1, s\}$. If s divides t , then any s -core partition is itself a t -core, so we are done. Suppose s does not divide t and $\gcd(s, t) > 1$. Removing a t -hook from ρ is equivalent to taking a bead x on the ℓ -th runner (for some ℓ between 0 and $s - 1$) of $\mathcal{A}^s(\beta(\rho))$ and placing it in empty position to the west in the $(\ell - t)$ -th runner. (For the remainder of this note, if $t > \ell$ we will interpret this difference as $\ell - t \pmod s$.) Removing another t -hook starting from a bead on the $(\ell - t)$ -th runner, we arrive at the $(\ell - 2t)$ -th runner, and so on, until eventually for some $j > 0$ we obtain $\ell - jt \equiv \ell \pmod s$. This suggests the following definition. A t -orbit of the s -abacus is a finite sequence (read from right-to-left) of distinct runners reached by repeated moves of t -positions west. Then, if $k' = \gcd(s, t)$, each t -orbit of $\mathcal{A}^s(\beta(\rho))$ will have exactly k' distinct runners. Starting from $\ell = 1$, for each value $1, 2, 3 \dots$ we denote by $\mathcal{O}_t(s - \ell)$ a t -orbit of runners which begins at the $(s - \ell)$ -th runner. Since for $0 \leq z, z' \leq s - 1$ and $z \neq z'$ either $\mathcal{O}_t(z) \cap \mathcal{O}_t(z') = \emptyset$ or $\mathcal{O}_t(z) = \mathcal{O}_t(z')$, there will be exactly $k = \frac{s}{k'}$ distinct t -orbits of $\mathcal{A}^s(\beta(\rho))$.

Now $\mathcal{O}_t(s - \ell)$ can itself be seen as a k' -abacus of runners plucked from $\mathcal{A}^{(s)}(\beta(\rho))$ and re-arranged in such a way that moving a bead one position west is equivalent to removing a t -hook from ρ . (Note: from the westmost runner removing a t -hook requires placing the bead one position north on the eastmost runner.) Viewed as a k' -abacus, moving a bead one position north in $\mathcal{O}_t(s - \ell)$ will still be equivalent to removing a s -hook from ρ , since it is comprised of runners of $\mathcal{A}^s(\beta(\rho))$. This construction is a variation of the (s, t) -abacus of J. Olsson and D. Stanton (see Section 5, [4]) which they define when s, t are relatively prime.

For all $1 \leq \ell \leq k$ the runners in $\mathcal{O}_t(s - \ell) \subset \mathcal{A}^s(\beta(\rho))$ will be labeled

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{O}_t(s - 1) &= (\beta(\rho)_{s-1-(k'-1)t}, \dots, \beta(\rho)_{s-1}) \\ &\vdots \\ \mathcal{O}_t(s - k) &= (\beta(\rho)_{s-k-(k'-1)t}, \dots, \beta(\rho)_{s-k}). \end{aligned}$$

For a fixed ℓ we obtain the t -core of $\mathcal{O}_t(s - \ell)$ by moving all available beads one position west on $\mathcal{O}_t(s - \ell)$ until we obtain a k' -abacus with no available westward moves. We denote this k' -abacus by $\widehat{\mathcal{O}}_t(s - \ell)$. It can be obtained systematically from $\mathcal{O}_t(s - \ell)$.

Algorithm for finding $\widehat{\mathcal{O}}_t(s - \ell)$. Let $i \in \{1, \dots, k'\}$ and $b_i = |\beta(\rho)_{(s-\ell)-(i-1)t}|$ be the number of beads in the runner i positions west on $\mathcal{O}_t(s - \ell)$. Then $B(1, 2) = b_1 - b_2$ is the difference between the number of beads in the eastmost or $(s - \ell)$ -th runner and the runner immediately to the west of it, the $(s - \ell - t)$ -th runner. If $B(1, 2)$ is negative or zero, move no beads. If $B(1, 2) = 2f$, place f of the southmost beads from the $(s - \ell)$ -th runner in the northmost empty spaces of the $(s - \ell - t)$ -th runner, so that the number of beads in the two runners now become equal. If $B(1, 2) = 2f + 1$, place the $f + 1$ of the southmost beads from the $(s - \ell)$ -th runner in the northmost empty spaces of $(s - \ell - t)$ -th runner, so that the runner to the west now has one more bead than the eastmost runner. For $i = 2, 3, \dots$ etc. follow the same procedure for $B(i, i + 1)$, except when $B = (k', 1) = 2f + 1$. In this case, place only f beads from the westmost runner in the northmost available empty spaces on the eastmost or $(s - \ell)$ -th runner. Repeating this procedure a finite number of times results in the modified subsequence $\widehat{\mathcal{O}}_t(s - \ell) = (\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_{s-\ell-(k'-1)t}, \dots, \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_{s-\ell})$ which when viewed as a k' -abacus has no available westward moves.

Finding the t -core of ρ . For each ℓ , obtain $\widehat{\mathcal{O}}_t(s - \ell)$ from $\mathcal{O}_t(s - \ell)$ as above. Then $\mathcal{A}^s(\widehat{\beta}(\rho)) = (\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_0, \dots, \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_{s-1})$ will be the s -abacus for the t -core of ρ . This follows by construction, since using the runners of the modified t -orbits $\widehat{\mathcal{O}}_t(s - \ell)$ implies there are no available moves t positions west. However $\mathcal{A}^s(\widehat{\beta}(\rho))$ still has no available moves one position north (by our algorithm) and hence remains an s -abacus of an s -core.

2. Examples

Example 2.1. Let $s = 6$ and $t = 3$. Consider the following 6-abacus $\mathcal{A}^6(\beta(\rho))$ of a 6-core ρ :

$\beta(\rho)_0$	$\beta(\rho)_1$	$\beta(\rho)_2$	$\beta(\rho)_3$	$\beta(\rho)_4$	$\beta(\rho)_5$
0	<u>1</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>3</u>	<u>4</u>	<u>5</u>
6	<u>7</u>	<u>8</u>	9	<u>10</u>	11
12	13	<u>14</u>	15	<u>16</u>	17
18	19	20	21	<u>22</u>	23.

Since $\gcd(6,3)=3$, we have $k = 3$ and $k' = \frac{6}{3} = 2$. Hence we have three 3-orbits $\mathcal{O}_t(s - \ell)$ (each with $k' = 2$ runners) and their corresponding 3-cores $\widehat{\mathcal{O}}_t(s - \ell)$:

	$\beta(\rho)_2$	$\beta(\rho)_5$		$\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_2$	$\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_5$
	<u>2</u>	<u>5</u>		<u>2</u>	<u>5</u>
$\mathcal{O}_3(1) =$	<u>8</u>	11	$\widehat{\mathcal{O}}_3(1) =$	<u>8</u>	<u>11</u>
	<u>14</u>	17		14	17
	20	23		20	23

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 & \beta(\rho)_1 & \beta(\rho)_4 & & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_1 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_4 \\
 \mathcal{O}_3(2) = & \underline{1} & \underline{4} & & \underline{1} & \underline{4} \\
 & \underline{7} & \underline{10} & \widehat{\mathcal{O}}_3(2) = & \underline{7} & \underline{10} \\
 & \underline{13} & \underline{16} & & \underline{13} & \underline{16} \\
 & \underline{19} & \underline{22} & & \underline{19} & \underline{22} \\
 \\
 & \beta(\rho)_0 & \beta(\rho)_3 & & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_0 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_3 \\
 \mathcal{O}_3(3) = & 0 & \underline{3} & & \underline{0} & \underline{3} \\
 & \underline{6} & \underline{9} & \widehat{\mathcal{O}}_3(3) = & \underline{6} & \underline{9} \\
 & \underline{12} & \underline{15} & & \underline{12} & \underline{15} \\
 & \underline{18} & \underline{21} & & \underline{18} & \underline{21}.
 \end{array}$$

Finally we obtain the 6-abacus $\mathcal{A}^6(\widehat{\beta}(\rho))$ of $\widehat{\rho}$ the 3-core of ρ :

$$\begin{array}{cccccc}
 \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_0 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_1 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_2 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_3 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_4 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_5 \\
 \underline{0} & \underline{1} & \underline{2} & \underline{3} & \underline{4} & \underline{5} \\
 \underline{6} & \underline{7} & \underline{8} & \underline{9} & \underline{10} & \underline{11} \\
 \underline{12} & \underline{13} & \underline{14} & \underline{15} & \underline{16} & \underline{17}.
 \end{array}$$

Example 2.2. Let $s = 12$ and $t = 8$. Consider the following 12-abacus $\mathcal{A}^{12}(\beta(\rho))$ of a 12-core ρ :

$\beta(\rho)_0$	$\beta(\rho)_1$	$\beta(\rho)_2$	$\beta(\rho)_3$	$\beta(\rho)_4$	$\beta(\rho)_5$	$\beta(\rho)_6$	$\beta(\rho)_7$	$\beta(\rho)_8$	$\beta(\rho)_9$	$\beta(\rho)_{10}$	$\beta(\rho)_{11}$
0	<u>1</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>3</u>	<u>4</u>	<u>5</u>	<u>6</u>	7	<u>8</u>	<u>9</u>	<u>10</u>	<u>11</u>
12	<u>13</u>	<u>14</u>	<u>15</u>	<u>16</u>	<u>17</u>	<u>18</u>	19	20	<u>21</u>	<u>22</u>	<u>23</u>
24	<u>25</u>	<u>26</u>	<u>27</u>	<u>28</u>	<u>29</u>	<u>30</u>	31	32	<u>33</u>	<u>34</u>	<u>35</u>
36	<u>37</u>	<u>38</u>	<u>39</u>	<u>40</u>	<u>41</u>	<u>42</u>	43	44	<u>45</u>	<u>46</u>	<u>47</u>
48	<u>49</u>	<u>50</u>	<u>51</u>	<u>52</u>	<u>53</u>	<u>54</u>	55	56	<u>57</u>	<u>58</u>	<u>59</u>
60	<u>61</u>	<u>62</u>	<u>63</u>	<u>64</u>	<u>65</u>	<u>66</u>	67	68	<u>69</u>	<u>70</u>	<u>71</u>

Since $\gcd(12,8)=4$, we have $k = 4$ and $k' = \frac{12}{4} = 3$. Hence we have four 8-orbits $\mathcal{O}_8(s - \ell)$ (each with $k' = 3$ runners) and their corresponding 8-cores $\widehat{\mathcal{O}}_8(s - \ell)$:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 \beta(\rho)_7 & \beta(\rho)_3 & \beta(\rho)_{11} & & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_7 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_3 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_{11} \\
 7 & \underline{3} & \underline{11} & & \underline{7} & \underline{3} & \underline{11} \\
 19 & \underline{15} & \underline{23} & & \underline{19} & \underline{15} & \underline{23} \\
 \mathcal{O}_8(1) = & 31 & \underline{27} & 35 & \widehat{\mathcal{O}}_8(1) = & \underline{31} & \underline{27} & 35 \\
 & 43 & \underline{39} & 47 & & 43 & \underline{39} & 47 \\
 & 55 & \underline{51} & 59 & & 55 & \underline{51} & 59 \\
 & 67 & \underline{63} & 71 & & 67 & \underline{63} & 71 \\
 \\
 \beta(\rho)_6 & \beta(\rho)_2 & \beta(\rho)_{10} & & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_6 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_2 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_{10} \\
 \underline{6} & \underline{2} & \underline{10} & & \underline{6} & \underline{2} & \underline{10} \\
 \underline{18} & \underline{14} & \underline{22} & & \underline{18} & \underline{14} & \underline{22} \\
 \mathcal{O}_8(2) = & \underline{30} & \underline{26} & \underline{34} & \widehat{\mathcal{O}}_8(2) = & \underline{30} & \underline{26} & \underline{34} \\
 & 42 & \underline{38} & \underline{46} & & 42 & \underline{38} & \underline{46} \\
 & 54 & \underline{50} & \underline{58} & & 54 & \underline{50} & \underline{58} \\
 & 66 & \underline{62} & \underline{70} & & 66 & \underline{62} & \underline{70}
 \end{array}$$

$$\mathcal{O}_8(3) = \begin{matrix} \beta(\rho)_5 & \beta(\rho)_1 & \beta(\rho)_9 \\ \underline{5} & \underline{1} & \underline{9} \\ 17 & \underline{13} & \underline{21} \\ 29 & \underline{25} & \underline{33} \\ 41 & \underline{37} & \underline{45} \\ 53 & 49 & \underline{57} \\ 65 & 61 & \underline{69} \end{matrix} \quad \widehat{\mathcal{O}}_8(3) = \begin{matrix} \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_5 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_1 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_9 \\ \underline{5} & \underline{1} & \underline{9} \\ \underline{17} & \underline{13} & \underline{21} \\ \underline{29} & \underline{25} & \underline{33} \\ \underline{41} & \underline{37} & 45 \\ 53 & 49 & 57 \\ 65 & 61 & 69 \end{matrix}$$

$$\mathcal{O}_8(4) = \begin{matrix} \beta(\rho)_4 & \beta(\rho)_0 & \beta(\rho)_8 \\ \underline{4} & 0 & \underline{8} \\ \underline{16} & 12 & 20 \\ \underline{28} & 24 & 32 \\ 40 & 36 & 44 \\ 52 & 48 & 56 \\ 64 & 60 & 68 \end{matrix} \quad \widehat{\mathcal{O}}_8(4) = \begin{matrix} \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_4 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_0 & \widehat{\beta}(\rho)_8 \\ \underline{4} & \underline{0} & \underline{8} \\ \underline{16} & 12 & 20 \\ 28 & 24 & 32 \\ 40 & 36 & 44 \\ 52 & 48 & 56 \\ 64 & 60 & 68. \end{matrix}$$

Finally we obtain the 12-abacus $\mathcal{A}^{12}(\widehat{\beta}(\rho))$ of $\widehat{\rho}$ the 8-core of ρ :

$\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_1$	$\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_2$	$\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_3$	$\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_4$	$\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_4$	$\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_5$	$\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_6$	$\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_7$	$\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_8$	$\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_9$	$\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_{10}$	$\widehat{\beta}(\rho)_{11}$
<u>0</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>3</u>	<u>4</u>	<u>5</u>	<u>6</u>	<u>7</u>	<u>8</u>	<u>9</u>	<u>10</u>	<u>11</u>
12	<u>13</u>	<u>14</u>	<u>15</u>	<u>16</u>	<u>17</u>	<u>18</u>	<u>19</u>	20	<u>21</u>	<u>22</u>	<u>23</u>
24	<u>25</u>	<u>26</u>	27	28	<u>29</u>	<u>30</u>	<u>31</u>	32	<u>33</u>	<u>34</u>	35
36	<u>37</u>	<u>38</u>	39	40	<u>41</u>	42	43	44	45	46	47
48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59
60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71.

For other results on partitions that are simultaneously s -cores and t -cores see [1], [3], [7].

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